

UTILIZATION OF ENGLISH GRAMMAR SUPPLEMENTARY INTERVENTION MATERIALS FOR VOICES OF VERBS AMONG GRADE 7 STUDENTS OF KAPAYAPAAN INTEGRATED SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effectiveness of utilizing the English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials in teaching active and passive voices among Grade 7 students of Kapayapaan Integrated School at Kapayapaan Ville Canlubang, Calamba City, Laguna. The research was guided by theories such as transformational generative grammar, structuralism, and constructivism, which aimed to lay the groundwork for a detailed exploration of active and passive voice through these prominent linguistic frameworks. Moreover, this study utilized a quasi-experimental research design, selecting Grade 7 students of Kapayapaan Integrated School through purposive sampling. A researcher-made questionnaire was used to gather data in line with the declared theories. Additionally, statistical analyses, including frequencies, percentages, means, and a paired t-test, were used to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention. The results demonstrated significant improvements in understanding active and passive voices. Furthermore, the findings revealed significant improvement in the use of active and passive voice among Grade 7 students after being exposed to the English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials. Posttest assessments revealed notable enhancements in understanding active and passive voices among the experimental group. The study reveals that a lack of mastery in verb tenses is a key factor hindering the understanding of active and passive voices. The study's outcome led to the development of an action plan titled "Project VIBE" (Verb Integration in Building Expertise), which emphasized skill building in verb use, especially on tenses and voices of verbs.

Keywords: *Utilization, Tenses and Voices of Verbs, Supplementary Intervention Materials, Teaching, English Grammar*

INTRODUCTION

The value of the English language is indisputable. It is the language used to converse with individuals from various nations. It is the language of business, science, technology, law, literature, the arts, sports, music, and international politics. Communicating in English opens up many chances both domestically and internationally. Indeed, learning grammar is crucial to learning English. It serves as the basis for both speaking and comprehending English. To utilize English correctly, learners must be aware of its grammar rules. It is important to learn because it makes it easier for learners to comprehend English. Grammar relies heavily on verbs, and a wide variety of verbs are used to express actions or show the state of being. Given that a sentence cannot exist without verbs, verbs are the most important part of speech because they can be used to ask a question or make a remark within a sentence, among other things. Linked periods of social development in every aspect of life, there are active and passive usage of English, and many try to use formal or informal English instruction.

Subsequently, voice is one component of grammar. Safarova (2024) stated that the idea of "voice" was a basic, yet complex, component of English grammar that greatly influenced sentence structure and meaning. The two main voices in English, the active and passive, had different linguistic structures and usage dynamics. Both the active voice, in which the subject took the initiative, and the passive voice, in which the subject was the one doing the action, had different stylistic and communicative roles.

In addition, Jobirovna (2023) mentioned that the categories of "Voice" and tense were closely related since they offer valuable insights into the internal temporal organization of structure. It was clearly stated that before learning the active and passive voices, the students should master the basics of grammar, such as identifying the two basic parts of a sentence – subject and predicate, rules in subject-verb agreement, and the tenses of verbs.

Previously, the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum of the Department of Education (2016, as cited in Flores, 2023) presented the framework in the English curriculum guide to provide essential knowledge and skills to its students to wit: The Language Arts and Multi-Literacies Curriculum's ultimate goal was to produce graduates who could apply language conventions, principles, strategies, and skills in three areas: (1) interacting with others, (2) understanding and learning other content areas, and (3) fending for themselves in whatever field of endeavor they may engage in. Given this framework, quality secondary English education, reflective of best practices in instruction, also entailed using varied, practical approaches and instructional materials in teaching, which would equip each learner with the necessary skills and competencies.

As such, students did not have the necessary English communication abilities when they started junior high school. The situation got worse because the new curricula's general education classes no longer included English grammar lessons, such as the basic sentence pattern, which has an impact on the students' writing performance. Consequently, these learners did not seem to be able to write properly, and their knowledge of speech elements is lacking. Their work was rife with run-on sentences, fragments, unparalleled ideas, and written in "text language." As a result, understanding the lesson taught in straight English could not be done by Filipino students. Besides, they could not construct grammatically correct sentences in stating their reflections or essays, and they did not even know the basic parts of sentences.

When the pandemic occurred, Philippine education became worse because many students were not properly taught the learning competencies they should acquire in English. AB Conservation 2022, in its article entitled Education Situation in the Philippines During CoViD-19 Pandemic, without access to the Internet and computers, was one of the problems experienced by Filipino students who were less fortunate. Many of them decided to quit studying due to uncertainty since they felt it was not worthwhile to continue learning during a pandemic using the standard method. In response to this problem, the Division Memorandum No. 185, s. of 2022, the Basic Education-Learning Recovery and Continuity Plan (BE-LRCP) for SY 2022–2023 established Guidelines on the Implementation of Project DREAM as Banner Initiative. These guidelines addressed the gaps in learners' literacy and numeracy skills and were implemented in all schools within the Division of Calamba City. Next, the Department of Education had implemented the National Learning Recovery Program through DepEd Order No. 013, s. 2023, which emphasized the need to repair learning losses among students brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic's disruption of in-person schooling.

One of the challenges in learning the English language was understanding grammatical rules, most especially the verbs. Additionally, the teaching of active and passive voices of verbs was one of the least learned competencies in English 7. Hence, they were not familiar with whether a subject was a doer or receiver of the action. As a consequence, the inability to speak English clearly and smoothly led to issues that could negatively impact scholastic achievement. In line with this, the teacher conducted an intervention program using the adopted material to develop students' learning of grammar with the verbs under voices. Similarly, the educational resources utilized in the research-based intervention program were necessary to customize techniques and lessons to meet the needs of the students.

This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials in teaching verb voices to Grade 7 English students and identify the underlying reasons for their difficulties in mastering this learning competency.

Research Questions:

The general aim of the study was to look into the use of English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials for active and passive voices and find out whether

it has greatly affected the grammar skills in the English language of Grade 7 students for the school year 2024-2025 at Kapayapaan Integrated School.

1. What is the pretest score of Grade 7 students in the control group in the voices of verbs?
2. What is the pretest score of Grade 7 students in the experimental group in the voices of verbs?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental groups?
4. What is the posttest score of Grade 7 students in the control group in the voices of verbs?
5. What is the posttest score of Grade 7 students in the experimental group in the voices of verbs?
6. Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental groups?
7. Is there a significant difference between pretest and posttest results of the control and experimental groups?
8. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

The research was carried out at Kapayapaan Integrated School, located in Manfil, Kapayapaan Ville Canlubang, Calamba City, Laguna.

Purposive sampling was employed in this study, which, according to Alchemer (2021, as cited in Alabanza, 2022) occurred when researchers carefully consider creating a study sample. The study purposively selected individuals with specific characteristics. Due to the researcher's selection of respondents, students with particular characteristics were selected through a purposive sampling technique.

The research population was the Grade 7 learners this school year 2024 – 2025 of Kapayapaan Integrated School. Currently, the number of sections is 15 and there are maximum of 45 students by section with a total of six hundred ten (654) learners.

Moreover, McCombes (2021, as cited in Alabanza, 2022) defined a sample as a subset of individuals taken from a broader population, and sampling is the process of determining which group would be used to collect data for the study. The study sample was divided into two groups, representing the control and experimental groups, as previously stated. Meanwhile, one section was the control group, wherein they were not given treatment, as the experimental group. The t-test was utilized to test the significance of the two sections which got the lowest means. The result proved that there were no significant differences between the two groups.

The respondents of the study were two (2) groups that came from different sections handled by the researcher in Grade 7 from Kapayapaan Integrated School located in

Canlubang, Calamba City, Laguna. The experimental group was exposed to a treatment consisting of using adopted workbook material “Supplementary Intervention Materials in English Grammar for Grade 7 Students,” and another for the control group, which was not exposed to any intervention. Group A was assigned to the control group, whereas Group B was assigned to the experimental group.

To establish objectivity in selecting respondents, a standardized diagnostic tool the General Assessment of Proficiency from the Division of Calamba City, was conducted. The scores of the GAP were arranged from highest to lowest in the 5 sections. A balanced number of 35 (high, average, and low-performing students) was made for control and experimental groups, for a total of 70 respondents.

According to Yazon et al. (2019, as cited in Alabanza, 2022) in the book “Learning Guide in Methods of Research,” pretest and posttest were the commonly used forms of testing in educational research, notably in intervention studies. The researcher-made instrument was used to gather all of the data necessary to assess the respondents’ learning of grammar in using the voices of verbs before and after utilizing the adopted material, “English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Material for Grade 7 Students.” It was also evaluated whether the aforementioned workbook material could assist learners in improving their grammar skills, particularly the voices of verbs. The test question was divided into 4 parts: choosing situations for the appropriate use of active and passive voices based on the situation, completing the correct verb form in the given active and passive sentences, identifying the passive forms based on the given active form sentences, and changing the active to passive voice sentences.

Since the instrument used was researcher-made, it was validated and approved by experts in the field. These experts contributed their efforts to addressing all necessary concerns clarified during the research process. Additionally, the researcher sought assistance from experts in research, including an adviser and several professors from LCBA, to validate the tool in terms of content, appropriateness, relevance, and clarity. The validation panel consisted of the Thesis Adviser, Statistician, Research Director, and two Master Teachers from the Department of Education. During the initial round of validation, some items were rejected by the validators. Revisions were made to the test items, which were subsequently approved. Finally, the data was computed to obtain the Lawshe Content Validity Index, yielding an acceptable CVI value of 1.00 for all test items.

The objectives of this research were to evaluate the effectiveness of intervention materials in enhancing the ability of Grade 7 students at Kapayapaan Integrated School to correctly use verbs, with a specific focus on understanding and applying active and passive voice. Additionally, the study aimed to identify the underlying reasons that contribute to students’ difficulties in mastering this learning competency. The test was answered by paper and pencil so that all students would be able to answer. The required documentation after obtaining permission to conduct this study is to verify that all phases were documented, supported, and formalized. An endorsement letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of Calamba City was written, followed by a letter given to the Principal of Kapayapaan Integrated School, where the study was conducted. Following

approval, permission letters were issued to the respondents' parents to demonstrate that their participation in this study was voluntary. The significance of the study, its objectives, the class schedule for groups A and B, and the benefits of conducting this research were discussed. This was made to facilitate easy access to all the respondents.

Initially, the Grade 7 students of Kapayapaan Integrated School answered the pretest to determine their ability in grammar lessons, most likely the verbs. The scores from each group were used to compare the findings. The results for the control and experimental groups were slightly the same because no teaching or intervention was conducted.

Subsequently, the experimental group received an intervention in which the researcher included the "English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials for Grade 7 students," which was used in classroom instruction. Most of the topics were about verbs, specifically the voices of verbs, which are stated in the Most Essential Learning Competency (EN7G-III-c2 Use the passive and active voice meaningfully in varied contexts.) The intervention took six weeks for the students to acquire mastery in active and passive voices.

The control group received no treatment or intervention; instead, they received the normal way of teaching about the active and passive voices. The two groups took a post-test after teaching the classes using the traditional way of teaching for the control group and the utilization of the adopted material "English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials" for the experimental group.

All data were collected, gathered, and tallied. The statistician received all of the obtained data and applied statistical treatment. Their scores were gathered and evaluated to determine whether any differences would emerge.

In gathering data, it was understood to use the quantitative research study, expressed in numbers measured systematically. A variety of methods and strategies were used to organize, develop, and elucidate such information methodically and accurately. The following were the statistical treatments applied to the study:

- 1. Frequency, Percentages, and Mean.** These were used to analyze the respondents' pretest and posttest results.
- 2. Paired T-test.** This was utilized to determine the significant differences between the pretest results of the control and experimental groups before and after the use of supplementary intervention material. Additionally, it helped identify the significant differences between the pretest and posttest results of both groups in Grade 7.

Initially, describing the limitations and scope of this study was vital to ensure that everyone was aware of them. This established the research project's boundaries and made the potential insights that could arise from its findings obvious.

This research focused on Grade 7 learners ages 12-14 years old who were enrolled at Kapayapaan Integrated School this school year 2024 - 2025. They made use of the English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials to acquire mastery of their grammar skills in active and passive voices with the integration of verb tenses and other concepts of verbs. The quasi-experimental design was used over 6 weeks for this experimentation process. Additionally, this investigation acknowledged its limitations. First, results could only be generalized to Grade 7 students of Kapayapaan Integrated School and could not be extended to other groups or educational settings. Furthermore, only grammar skills in English, specifically the voices of verbs, including the verb tenses, were measured. Third, the English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials did not assess the other comparable reference materials or the findings across the junior high school population. Fourth, sample size restrictions limited applicability in general to findings across a wider school population.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question Number 1. What is the pretest score of Grade 7 students in the control group in the voices of verbs?

Table 1
Pretest Score of Grade 7 Students in the Control Group

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Outstanding	0	0%
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	0	0%
80 – 84	Satisfactory	7	20%
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory	8	22.86%
74 and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	20	57.14%
	Total	35	100%
	Standard Deviation	4.455	
	Overall Performance	73.07	

The overall pretest score of the students in the control group in the pretest was 73.07 with a standard deviation of 4.455. Furthermore, 57.14% or 20 out of 35 students in the control group did not meet expectations, 22.86% or 8 out of 35 were Fairly Satisfactory, while 20% or only 7 out of 35 were Satisfactory.

According to the findings, learners have no prior knowledge of grammar, particularly in active and passive voices. Students with no schema of verb tenses tend to struggle with both understanding and producing active and passive sentences.

To support the findings above, Nurussa'adah et al. (2024) stated that students were confused about grammar, especially in active and passive voices, because of a lack of understanding of English grammar. Occasionally, they are unaware of when their writing has errors. It occurs as a result of their zero knowledge of English. The challenge of

utilizing verbs is one of the factors for not understanding active and passive voices. When converting active voice to passive voice, students are likely to make mistakes if they were not knowledgeable about the irregular and regular forms of verbs.

The result was nearly identical to the study of Darohim (2020), which revealed that students' poor comprehension is based on their unfamiliarity with verb modifications and the usage of the verb "to be" and subject placement. The final one, inadequate comprehension, also stems from a lack of prior information and context awareness in constructing active to passive voices.

Research Question Number 2. What is the pretest score of Grade 7 students in the experimental group in the voices of verbs?

Table 2
Pretest Score of Grade 7 Students in the Experimental Group

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Outstanding	0	0%
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	0	0%
80 – 84	Satisfactory	4	11.42%
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory	9	25.71%
74 and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	22	62.86%
	Total	35	100%
	Standard Deviation	4.331	
	Overall Performance	72.07	

The overall pretest score of the students in the experimental group was **72.07** with a standard deviation of **4.331**. Furthermore, **62.86%** or 22 out of 35 students in the experimental group did not meet expectations, 25.71% or 9 out of 35 were Fairly Satisfactory, while 11.42% or only 4 out of 35 were Satisfactory.

This means that Grade 7 students in the experimental group also have no prior knowledge of grammar about active and passive voices. Students in the experimental group are also clueless of verb tenses and this results to lower levels of understanding of active and passive voices before receiving any instructional intervention, confirming their lack of prior knowledge.

To support the findings above, Sari et al. (2022) claimed that a lack of vocabulary mastery and having less knowledge of regular and irregular verbs in the past participle are factors in committing errors in using active and passive voices. Students utilized the passive voice incorrectly because they didn't comprehend the meaning of a few active voice terms. It was known that certain mistakes were made because the pupils struggled to convert active voices into simple past tense passive voices. They were unable to convert verbs one or two into the past tense or verb three.

As per Fadhilawati et al. (2022), due to its complexity, many pupils were unable to understand this lesson on passive voice. They also mentioned that students would find it challenging to write or speak effectively if they lack a solid understanding of grammar regarding tenses of verbs. Numerous factors were mentioned as to why this lesson is difficult, such as limited time for studying passive voice, lack of reviews, and the last period in the class.

Research Question Number 3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental groups?

Table 3
Test of Significant Difference between the Pretest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

		Paired Differences				Remarks	Decision
		Mean	SD	T	P value		
Pretest Control and Experimental Groups	Score	.800000	6.83331	.693	.493	Not Significant	Accept H ₀

There was **no significant difference** between the mean scores of the students from the control and experimental groups on the pretest. The probability value was **.493**, which was greater than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted.

The finding suggests that the Grade 7 students in the control and experimental groups have the same level of knowledge at the beginning of the experiment. There are no differences in their pretest results. Both groups have no statistically significant differences, which indicates that they are all at or near the same level of least learned competency in using verbs, particularly the active and passive voices. These students do not have good practice of independent learning or good study habits for them to acquire mastery in verb tenses and verb voices. A lack of interest in learning English, as well as an understanding of grammar, can be a factor.

Generally, since the test was intended to determine the grammar skills of students in using verbs, specifically the voices of verbs, the “not significant” result can be attributed to not yet utilizing the English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Material.

Moreover, Apse and Farneste (2020) stated that insufficient practice of independent learning was one of the reasons why students struggled in distinguishing the use of present and past tenses and voices in the given context. Students who studied independently must reflect on their education, that is, exercise responsibility.

Further support was found in the study of Idami and Pratiwi (2021), which stated that students' lack of interest in studying English, together with their inability to acquire vocabulary and comprehend grammar, were internal issues.

Research Question Number 4. What is the posttest score of Grade 7 students in the control group in the voices of verbs?

Table 4
Posttest Score of Grade 7 Students in the Control Group

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Outstanding	13	37.14%
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	21	60%
80 – 84	Satisfactory	1	2.85%
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory	0	0%
74 and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0%
	Total	35	100%
	Standard Deviation	2.44949	
	Overall Performance	88.75	

The overall posttest score of the students in the control group was **88.75** with a standard deviation of **2.449**. Furthermore, 60% or 21 out of 35 students in the control group were Very Satisfactory, 37.14 % or 13 out of 35 were Outstanding, while 2.85% or only 1 out of 35 were Satisfactory.

The results for the Grade 7 students have improved in the control group, showing a very satisfactory level of performance in understanding the active and passive voices and verb tenses as well. Thirteen (13) students achieved an outstanding score on the posttest. These students were very active in class during the teaching delivery time, and they also provided extra time to do their assignments, specifically memorizing the past tense and past participle of the verbs, which are prerequisites to learning active and passive voices.

Most of them acquired mastery in the voices of verbs because of the procedures or steps to follow in changing active to passive voice.

In the same way, Hanim et al. (2024) claimed that students employed two ways to get beyond learning challenges. The first is using formulas to help them master the active and passive voices. The second is doing a lot of active and passive exercises to understand this grammar lesson. Diyata (2022) stated that a procedural form with integrated steps serves as a guide for students as they work through the activities. It is believed that by using this strategy, the students would know how active phrases were changed to passive ones. He also claimed that the students who have a better understanding of tense knowledge would be able to comprehend the passive sentence content.

To support the claim that active participation in learning English grammar was a great help in English, Ravshanbek (2024) stated that using and practicing active grammar principles, one could become a better speaker and communicate more effectively with assurance.

Research Question Number 5. What is the posttest score of Grade 7 students in the experimental group in the voices of verbs?

Table 5
Posttest Score of Grade 7 Students in the Experimental Group in the Voices of Verbs

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Outstanding	20	57.14%
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	15	42.86%
80 – 84	Satisfactory	0	0%
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory	0	0%
74 and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0%
	Total	35	100%
	Standard Deviation	2.99944	
	Overall Performance	90.82	

The overall posttest score of the students in the experimental group was **90.82** with a standard deviation of **2.999**. Furthermore, **57.14%** or 20 out of 35 students in the experimental group were Outstanding, 42.86 % or 15 out of 35 were Very Satisfactory. None of them belonged to a lower performance level. As a result, there had been an increase of 18.75 from 72.07 to 90.82.

The results show that the students' learning has improved, especially in verb tenses, active and passive voice sentence construction, and the formation of the s-form and base form of the verbs. The experimental group's learners demonstrated a high proficiency in grammar, particularly regarding verb tenses and voices. Additionally, they are now familiar with the grammar structure addressed in the test. It may be concluded that the student's understanding of verbs, particularly their tenses and voices, has improved with the aid of English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials for Grade 7 students.

To support this claim that intervention is a great help in students' performance in grammar, particularly with the active and passive voice, Flores (2023) stated that after using the material English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Material, students' grammatical proficiency has improved, going from low performing to fairly competent. It is quite legitimate, nevertheless, to say that they still need to work on their grammar to help their writing abilities and writing skills. Additionally, they had a positive attitude toward the content and thought it was very helpful and efficient.

Moreover, Harahap (2020) concluded that selecting a decent and appropriate method like EGRA (Exposure, Generalization, Reinforcement, and Application) in teaching passive voice would make the structure easier to understand the passive voice.

Additionally, EGRA can assist students in comprehending passive phrases, enhance their grammar proficiency, increase their willingness to learn, and cultivate soft skills like teamwork, self-assurance, communication, and the ability to think critically when solving problems.

Research Question Number 6. Is there a significant difference between the posttest results of the control and experimental groups in the voices of verbs?

Table 6
Test of Significant Difference between the Posttest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

	Differences				Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	T	P value		
Posttest Score Control and Experimental Groups	-1.65714	3.85733	-3.368	.016	Significant	Reject H_0

There was a significant difference between the mean scores of the students from the control and experimental groups on the posttest. The probability value was **.016**, which is less than the level of significance at **.05**. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. On the posttest of the two groups, it was very clear that the control and experimental groups performed very differently and significantly.

The control and experimental groups have significant differences because both groups had good results in the posttest. Another effect is that the experimental group showed nearly mastery-level English grammar after being exposed to the English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials in particularly with verb tenses and active and passive voices during their intervention period.

As mentioned by Eragamreddy (2024), the following methods such as EGRA technique, task-based learning, cooperative learning, flashcards, and web-based storytelling were found to be effective methods for teaching passive voice. It has been shown that applying these techniques improves learning results and comprehension as well as student involvement. Additionally, it was discovered that context-based learning was crucial to understanding when and how to use the passive voice efficiently, highlighting the need for flexible teaching methods that consider real-world situations.

Research Question Number 7. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores of the control and experimental groups?

Table 7.1
Test of Significant Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Control Group

	Paired Differences				Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	T	P value		
Pretest and Posttest of Control Group	-12.543	3.50078	-21.197	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

There was a significant difference between the mean scores of the students in the pretest and the posttest of the control group. The probability value was .000, which was less than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

It is noteworthy that significant improvements are observed in the pretest and the posttest of the control group. Before the students underwent such a normal way of teaching in the control group, most of them belonged to the low-performing. They are confused about subject-verb agreement, using correct forms of verbs, and verb tenses, which are essential in learning the active and passive voices.

In support of the findings above, Pereira et al. (2019, as cited in Islamy and Kaniadewi, 2022) studied the use of collaborative learning to teach passive voice to secondary students. Their study might be explained by the notable variations between the periods before and after passive voice instruction was introduced. This technique, in addition to the fun exercises and education in the classroom, supports one another. It might serve as a creative approach to instructing the learner on how to collaborate with others to expand their expertise, solving problems to enhance passive voice learning and gain a deeper knowledge. In the same way, research has been done by Syafina (2022, as cited in Islamy, 2022) on how the discussion approach can help students become more proficient in the use of the passive voice.

Table 7.2
Test of Significant Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group

	Paired Differences				Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	T	P value		
Pretest and Posttest of Experimental Group	-15.000	3.88057	-22.868	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

There was a significant difference between the mean scores of the students in the pretest and the posttest of the experimental group. The probability value was **.000**, which was less than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the **null hypothesis was rejected**.

It could be inferred from the results that the learners in the experimental group had improved from being low performers to high performers in learning verbs, particularly in the active and passive voice. During the pretest, the students were not knowledgeable about the verb changes that needed to be mastered first before learning the voices of verbs. After the posttest, the students showed significant improvement in their understanding of active and passive voices.

Overall, the results of the pretest and posttest in the experimental group were impressive, and the intervention conducted helped students achieve better learning outcomes. Therefore, the notable difference in student performance between the pretest and posttest results in both the control and experimental groups highlighted several critical factors that contributed to the outcomes of this study.

Firstly, the mastery of basic grammar lessons focused on verbs was essential, as a strong foundation in this area allowed students to better understand and apply grammatical rules effectively. Additionally, the teaching strategies employed played a significant role in facilitating student engagement and comprehension. The use of targeted intervention materials, designed to reinforce learning and provide practical applications, further enhanced students' grasp of the concepts being taught. Moreover, the active participation of students in the learning process fostered a collaborative and supportive environment that encouraged exploration and reinforced understanding.

Together, these elements—mastery of grammatical concepts, effective teaching strategies, well-developed intervention materials, and high levels of student engagement—were instrumental in producing a substantial difference in the results observed in this study. This underscored the importance of a comprehensive approach to teaching grammar, which not only improved student performance but also promoted a deeper understanding of language use.

Supporting the findings, Syafina (2022, as cited in Islamy, 2022) conducted a study on how the discussion approach could help students become more proficient in the use of the passive voice. Using this approach, the students demonstrated their understanding of the passive voice without relying on the teacher. Similarly, Pereira et al. (2019, as cited in Eragamreddy, 2024) showed that using collaborative learning to teach the passive voice was an effective method. Following group projects, students' assessments indicated a significant increase in understanding. This illustrates the efficacy of interactive learning strategies in grammar instruction.

Research Question Number 8. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

The action plan, Project VIBE (Verb Integration in Building Expertise), emphasized skill-building in verb use, particularly in tenses and voices of verbs. It was based on the findings of this study and was presented as follows.

Key Result Area	Objectives	Strategies/ Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Source of Fund	Success Indicators
Understanding of Verb Tenses	To acquire mastery in understanding all concepts about verbs	Practice drills use the English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials	July-August 2025 First Quarter Once a week	English Teachers Grade 7 Learners	School's Budget	99.9% of the objectives have been attained.
Tense Identification Exercise	To recognize the appropriate verb tense in the sentence	Identify and categorize sentences by their tenses using the intervention material	September 2025 First Quarter Once a week	English Teachers Grade 7 Learners	School's Budget	99.9% of the objectives have been attained.
Active and Passive Voice Overview	To use the patterns/formula in forming sentences using active and passive voices	<u>Seatworks</u> Interactive Group Work Shared reading of literary text In reading month, students will read literary text with the integration of tenses and voices of verbs.	October to November 2025 Second Qtr- Once a week National Reading Month	English Teachers Grade 7 Learners	School's Budget	99.9% of the objectives have been attained.
Sentence Transformation Practice	To construct grammatically correct sentences in journalistic and non-journalistic texts	Guided practice in converting sentences in journalistic and non-journalistic texts (aligned to MATATAG Curriculum)	December – January 2026 Once a week	English Teachers Grade 7 Learners	School's Budget	99.9% of the objectives have been attained.

The goal of Project VIBE was to emphasize to students the use of verb tenses and voices by creating a curriculum, implementing formative assessments, applying feedback techniques, designing interactive learning activities, teaching effective study habits, and continuously monitoring student progress through frequent assessments and data analysis. This approach sought to highlight the importance of verb tenses and voices to students. Additionally, it enhanced Grade 7 students' understanding and application of verb tenses and active/passive voices through integrated, engaging, and interactive learning experiences, ultimately building their expertise in effective communication.

By achieving these goals and objectives, Project VIBE aimed to create a lasting impact on students' language skills, fostering confidence in their ability to use verbs effectively in their academic and personal writing.

To align this with the MATATAG Curriculum, integrating the active and passive voice in the analysis of journalistic and non-journalistic texts, such as expository essays, encouraged students to critically assess the role of sentence construction in shaping tone, focus, and intent. This fostered a deeper comprehension of the author's message and purpose in both literary and non-literary contexts.

This action plan was aligned with the MATATAG Curriculum's goal of enabling students to demonstrate their knowledge of grammatical structures and apply their understanding of literary and informational texts. It aided in the development of writing skills by emphasizing the strategic use of active and passive voices, helping students structure their journalistic reports and expository essays with precision and purpose.

Conclusions

The study's findings, which were previously mentioned, led to the following conclusions:

1. That the Grade 7 students in the control group during their pretest have zero knowledge of the verbs, particularly with active and passive voice sentences. Learners with no prior knowledge or exposure to verb tenses face considerable challenges in both comprehending and producing sentences in active and passive forms.

2. That the Grade 7 students in the experimental group during their pretest also have no prior knowledge of grammar, in particular with active and passive voices, because they are clueless about verb tenses. The lower levels of understanding observed before any instructional intervention further confirm their lack of familiarity with these grammatical structures.

3. That there is no discernible difference in the pretest scores for active and passive voice usage between the experimental and control groups at the beginning of the study. There are no statistically significant differences between the two groups in the pretest results because they do not practice independent learning, indicating that they were at the same level in using verbs, particularly active and passive voices, before the implementation and execution of this study.

4. That the Grade 7 learners in the control group during posttest have demonstrated significant improvement in understanding both active and passive voices and verb tenses. Thirteen students achieved outstanding scores on the posttest, highlighting their active engagement during lessons and their commitment to extra practice, particularly in memorizing the past tense and past participles of verbs. This additional effort, along with following structured procedures for transforming active to passive voice, contributed to their mastery of the concept.

5. That the supplementary intervention material has beneficial effects because most of the students in the experimental group attain outstanding results in active and passive voice. The use of English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Material for Grade 7 Students has played a key role in enhancing their grasp of these concepts. This suggests that additional resources and targeted support can effectively reinforce students' foundational knowledge of grammar, leading to better comprehension and application of verb tenses and voices.

6. That the control and experimental groups have different performances after the posttest, as there is a difference between their posttest scores. The control and experimental groups' posttest results clearly show a significant difference. It can be concluded that the changes in performance happened after the implementation and execution of the adopted material, "English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Material for Grade 7 Students," to the experimental group. Students' comprehension of active and passive voice is greatly improved by conducting intervention with the integration of verb tenses in the experimental group, which is a little bit higher than that of the control group.

7. That the students in the control and experimental groups acquired mastery in learning the lesson on active and passive voices. The notable improvement in scores indicates that the instructional methods used in both groups were effective in enhancing students' understanding of active and passive voice. This suggests that the strategies employed, whether traditional or innovative, successfully addressed the learning objectives related to these grammatical concepts. The improvement in test scores suggests that the students not only learned the material but also retained it effectively over time. That as the output of this study, an action plan entitled "Project VIBE" can help the learners in coping with the areas in grammar, in particular with verbs, which they are struggling, such as the use of verb tenses, forms of the verb, and active and passive voice.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are strongly encouraged in light of the findings and conclusions:

1. By combining clear instruction, interactive practice, and regular assessment, students can gradually develop a strong grasp of active and passive voices, ensuring they move beyond their initial lack of knowledge in verb tenses and gain confidence in using these structures. Educators are encouraged to implement interactive and engaging teaching strategies that encourage student participation, such as group discussions, role-playing activities, and peer teaching. These methods can help students better understand the practical applications of active and passive constructions in real-life contexts.

2. It is crucial to incorporate regular, contextualized exercises that focus on verb tense mastery, allowing students to practice constructing sentences in both voices while reinforcing their understanding of verb forms. Providing visual aids, such as charts and diagrams, can also clarify the relationships between different tenses and voices, making complex concepts more accessible. Furthermore, utilizing technology and digital resources, such as grammar apps and online quizzes, can facilitate individualized learning and offer immediate feedback to students. Teachers might also conduct formative assessments to monitor progress and identify areas where students may struggle, allowing for timely interventions and targeted support.

3. By combining scaffolding, engagement, and interactive practice, teachers can provide a comprehensive and supportive learning environment that will enable students in the control and experimental groups to overcome their initial lack of knowledge and gain mastery over active and passive voices.

4. Considering the posttest result of the Grade 7 learners in the control group, the teachers may use the adopted material “English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Material for Grade 7 Students” in teaching verbs, particularly with the verb tenses and voices of verbs.

5. Given the posttest result of the Grade 7 learners in the experimental group, teachers may continue the use of “English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Material for Grade 7 Students” with the integration of ICT in teaching the verb tenses and voices of verbs. Furthermore, utilizing technology and digital resources, such as grammar apps and online quizzes, can facilitate individualized learning and offer immediate feedback to students.

6. Since there is a significant change in the performance of the control and experimental groups after the implementation and execution of the “English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials for Grade 7 Students,” it is recommended to continue this intervention material in teaching. Overall, the sustained use of supplementary intervention materials not only enriches the curriculum but also fosters a more dynamic and interactive classroom atmosphere conducive to learning.

7. Since there has been a significant change in the performance of the control and experimental groups during the pretest and posttest, continuing the use of “English Grammar Supplementary Intervention Materials for Grade 7 Students” can be highly effective to the Grade 7 learners in enhancing the teaching of active and passive voices. This material, which may include interactive worksheets, multimedia presentations, and online quizzes, provides diverse approaches to reinforce concepts. Engaging students with varied resources caters to different learning styles, making the lesson more accessible and enjoyable. Incorporating activities like group discussions and role-playing can further solidify their understanding by allowing them to practice transforming sentences from active to passive voice in a collaborative environment. Additionally, using real-life examples and contextual scenarios can help students relate to the material, thus increasing their interest and retention of knowledge.

8. The proposed output of this study, an action plan entitled “Project VIBE” may be used to aid learners in coping with the areas in which they are struggling, such as forms of verbs, verb tenses, and active and passive voices, is hereby recommended for approval. This project enhances Grade 7 students' understanding and application of verb tenses and active/passive voices through integrated, engaging, and interactive learning experiences, ultimately building their expertise in effective communication. Through Project VIBE, educators can create an engaging and supportive learning environment that not only deepens students' understanding of grammar about active and passive voices but also enhances their overall communication skills.

9. Future researchers may enhance interventions and teaching practices for active and passive voices in Grade 7 students may consider several key recommendations. First, it is crucial to design interventions that are grounded in evidence-based instructional strategies, such as the gradual release model, which encourages students to move from guided practice to independent application. Incorporating technology, such as interactive software and online platforms, can provide dynamic learning experiences and immediate feedback, fostering student engagement and understanding. Collaboration with teachers in the development and execution of these interventions is essential, as their insights and experiences can enhance the relevance and applicability of research findings. Furthermore, including real-world contexts and writing tasks that require students to use both active and passive voice will help them see the practical applications of grammar. Finally, longitudinal studies examining the long-term retention of skills and concepts can provide deeper insights into the effectiveness of different teaching practices over time. By focusing on these recommendations, researchers can significantly improve the teaching and learning of active and passive voices in Grade 7 students, leading to more effective language acquisition.

Compliance with the Ethical Standards

The author hereby declares that all ethical standards in conducting the study were strictly observed. Informed consent was properly secured from all participants, and they were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any stage without any consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were protected, and all procedures complied with Data Privacy regulations. The well-being and rights of the participants were safeguarded throughout the research process. Furthermore, the author affirms that no conflict of interest influenced the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, and the interpretation of findings remained objective and free from bias. The results obtained were utilized solely for academic and research purposes. In cases where Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools were utilized, full disclosure was properly acknowledged by the author.

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